

A New Lower Bound for Snake-in-the-Box in a 10-Dimensional Hypercube

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Abstract. The Snake-in-the-Box problem is the challenge of finding the longest possible induced path in the edge graph of an n -dimensional hypercube. Although the problem is unsolved in hypercubes of dimension 9 and above, research continues to refine lower and upper bounds on maximum possible path length. This paper demonstrates a new lower bound of 373 in the 10-dimensional case and describes the heuristics used in its discovery.

1 Introduction

The n -dimensional hypercube graph Q_n is a regular graph with 2^n vertices and $n \cdot 2^{n-1}$ edges. The Snake-in-the-Box problem seeks to find the longest induced path in Q_n . No two non-consecutive vertices in a snake's path may be adjacent to each other on the hypercube, a constraint that is essential to the character and complexity of the problem.

Figure 1 shows a 3-dimensional hypercube (i.e., a cube) with unit-length edges and one vertex at the origin. Vertices are labeled with binary numbers 000 through 111 formed from Cartesian coordinates. The red path shows a length-4 snake with vertex sequence 000, 001, 011, 111, 110.

Fig. 1. A snake in 3 dimensions.

Numbering vertices in binary allows for concise expression of the constraints in the Snake-in-the-Box problem: labels of consecutive vertices in a snake's path differ in exactly one bit position (i.e., have Hamming distance 1) whereas labels

of non-consecutive vertices differ in multiple bit positions (Hamming distance > 1). The Snake-in-the-Box problem arose in the study of coding theory [2] and continues to have application in that field. Thomas Drapela's primer [1] reviews the history of the problem.

2 Search tree

Transition sequence notation for snakes is a frequently-used alternative to vertex sequence notation. In a transition sequence, each edge of a snake is labeled with the position of the bit that varies between the labels for the two vertices incident to that edge, i.e. the base 2 logarithm of the bitwise exclusive OR of the vertices' binary labels. By convention, the initial vertex is at the origin. Transition sequence notation for the snake in Figure 1 is thus 0,1,2,0. Commas are often omitted in transition sequences.

The set of transition sequences for all possible snakes starting from the origin of a hypercube can be organized in a tree whose root node is a degenerate (empty transition sequence) snake. Transition sequences for each node's children are formed by appending digits corresponding to growth of the path in directions that create legal snakes.

Fig. 2. The complete tree of snakes in 3 dimensions.

Figure 2 shows the tree for the cube as shown in Figure 1. The first step in a path from the origin can traverse an edge in any of the three spatial dimensions. The second step can continue in either of two directions. There is only one legal choice of direction for the third and fourth edges added. Thereafter no further extension of a snake is possible. The tree for 3 dimensions is small enough to be exhaustively searched at a glance, revealing that the longest possible snake in a cube has 4 edges.

The trend of decreasing branching factor in successive levels of the tree is characteristic of the Snake-in-the-Box problem. Options for continued growth of a snake dwindle as the snake grows to occupy more vertices of the hypercube.

Figure 2 shows that there are six possible length-4 snakes starting from the origin of a cube. Their shapes are however not unique; they are all the same snake as transformed by the symmetries of a cube. Naïvely searching the entire

tree is clearly wasteful. It is more efficient to prune the tree to contain only one snake from each equivalence class of intertransformable snakes. To that end, Kochut [4] described a canonical form of transition sequence that requires new directions to be introduced in ascending order when extending a snake. Thus:

- the first digit in a transition sequence must be zero
- each subsequent digit must either be one of digits preceding it or one more than the maximum preceding digit in the sequence.

Following those rules, there is only one choice available at each level of the tree of snakes in 3 dimensions. The tree in Figure 2 prunes down to the single path on its left edge leading to leaf node 0120. There is no loss of generality, i.e. a tree pruned by this method will contain an instance of the longest possible snake in a hypercube.

Pruning by canonical form is worthwhile but it scarcely puts a dent in the combinatorial explosion that makes trees for hypercubes of dimension 9 or higher monstrously large. Extensive pruning is required to profitably search trees of snakes in high-dimensional hypercubes.

3 Ensuring legal snakes

Any program which extends a snake step by step needs a method for distinguishing between legal choices of direction and choices which would bring the snake too close to itself. An obvious method is to mark vertices adjacent to a snake as off-limits. Alternatively, the same effect can be achieved by marking edges that lead to off-limits vertices. The length-373 snake presented in this paper was found with a program that marks edges. The marking procedure is an implementation detail but it's worth describing for how it gathers information to be used by the program's tree-pruning heuristics.

Fig. 3. Edges marked as unusable when node 10000 is added to a snake.

Figure 3 shows a sample subgraph of a 5-dimensional hypercube graph. In this example, assume that a snake has just been extended to vertex 10000 and that all other vertices in the diagram were unaffected by previous growth of the snake. The task is to preclude adjacent vertices 10001 and 10010 from being added to the snake in the future.

All five hypercube edges incident to vertex 10011 are shown in the diagram. Up to now, all five were usable. But with the advent of vertex 10000 being added

to the snake, two edges (shown in red) are now marked as unusable. If vertex 10011 is added to the snake in the future, the program will not consider taking the next step via either of the edges shown in red.

Figure 3 only shows the marking of edges associated with vertex 10011. The complete marking procedure iterates through all vertices at Hamming distance 2 from vertex 10000, marking two edges incident to each vertex.

The program associates with each hypercube vertex an integer whose bits indicate which edges incident to that vertex are marked unusable. In the example shown in Figure 3, the program would set the two least significant bits in the integer associated with vertex 10011.

In this example, vertex 10011 loses the use of two of its five edges. But that isn't always the case. Sometimes one of the edges being marked will already have been marked unusable at an earlier stage in the snake's growth. This is useful information; losing two usable edges is a greater loss of resources than losing only one. The cumulative count of edges lost will be used in tree pruning.

The program also takes note when it reduces a vertex's count of remaining usable edges to fewer than two, as that leaves the vertex unusable for inclusion in the middle of a snake.

4 Heuristic Tree Search

The program which found a length-373 snake in 10 dimensions performs a heuristically-pruned breadth-first search of a tree of possible snakes structured as shown in Figure 2.

No more than two levels of the tree are represented in memory at any given time. After all children of a level's nodes have been generated, memory for the parent nodes is freed for future use.

Each node in the tree represents a snake and the hypercube it inhabits. The data for each node includes 2^d integers, one for each vertex in a d -dimensional hypercube. Bits in each integer indicate which edges incident on the vertex are marked unavailable as described in Section 3.

The program starts pruning the tree when generating all of a level's children would exceed the amount of available memory. This is based on an estimate, as the exact branching factor for the next level cannot be known in advance.

The program prunes by discarding a portion of the nodes at the current level. The next level generated will contain all legal children of the nodes that were not discarded.

Selecting which nodes to discard is guided by a scoring function that disfavors nodes deemed less likely to lead to a long snake. Such scoring is inherently imperfect and runs the risk of discarding nodes with the best future prospects.

The program discards nodes whose score exceeds a threshold calculated to ensure that generating next-level children will not exceed memory limitations.

The scoring function is a weighted sum of:

- the count of hypercube edges marked as unavailable
- the count of hypercube vertices with fewer than two available incident edges.

Tree search with pruning guided by this scoring function easily finds maximal-length snakes in up to 7 dimensions and a length-97 snake in 8 dimensions (where 98 is the maximum possible). In dimensions 9 and higher, its results lag increasingly farther behind published results from other methods.

The program that found a length-373 snake in 10 dimensions added a stochastic component to the pruning method: each snake is extended in multiple independent trials of depth-first search that chooses randomly among legal directions at each step. Snakes are ranked by the longest snake found in 100 trials; snakes in the top 10% of their level of the tree are exempted from pruning. The snakes in the bottom 90% are selectively pruned as guided by the scoring function based on counts of edges and vertices as described above.

These heuristics have not been extensively tuned. They are presented here to document the process by which an increment in best-known Snake-in-the-Box length came about. The previous record length the author is aware of in 10 dimensions is 370, dating to 2012 [3] and also found by a stochastic tree search technique, albeit a different one than used here.

5 Results

To search for a 10-dimensional snake, the program as described herein was primed with the length-190 9-dimensional snake given by Wynn [6], with further search restricted to an adjacent 9-dimensional space. Kinny [3] notes that “priming is an inherently unsafe method for finding optimal snakes. Nonetheless, priming the search with near-optimal snakes in the next lower dimension is a widely-used technique to make search tractable.”

The program was written in C++, compiled by gcc, and run under Ubuntu Linux. Running in 15 parallel threads on an Intel i5-12600K processor with pruning set to limit the approximate count of children generated in each layer of the tree to 13 million, the program takes six hours to extend the length-190 snake with 183 additional edges, giving a snake of length 373 in 10 dimensions. Most of the CPU time is consumed by the stochastic depth-first search trials.

The transition sequence for a length-373 snake is given in the Appendix as part of a program which verifies its correctness.

6 Summary

A length-373 path sets a new lower bound for Snake-in-the-Box in 10 dimensions. No single technique led to this result but rather a combination of search space heuristics, stochastic depth-first-search, and the joining of permuted lower-dimensional snakes [6] which provided the seed used to prime this search.

7 Acknowledgements

Thanks to Randall Munroe, whose comic xkcd #3125 [5] introduced the author to Snake-in-the-Box.

Thanks to everyone who's written about the Snake-in-the-Box problem and especially to Ed Wynn, who found the endearingly symmetric length-190 snake in 9 dimensions [6] that provided the seed for the snake described in this paper.

References

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4. K. J. Kochut, Snake-In-The-Box codes for dimension 7, *Journal of Combinatorial Mathematics and Combinatorial Computing* 20 (1996) 175–185.
5. R. Munroe, SNAKE-IN-THE-BOX PROBLEM, <https://xkcd.com/3125/> (2025).
6. E. Wynn, Constructing circuit codes by permuting initial sequences, arXiv:1201.1647v1 (2012).

A Appendix

The following C program validates a recently-discovered length-373 snake.

```
#include <stdio.h>

static const char transitions[] =
"0120314021 0541021432 1026431450 4134210431 4501432731 2014301263"
"2143053102 3053145036 0431402143 1046806104 3145014310 6302143203"
"5043203145 3654031405 4375314021 4310451341 0214316504 5314504120"
"4501430540 9804503410 5402140541 3046134120 1431540134 1204135734"
"5041304563 5413023405 3023412036 0134105413 4016285613 4120143154"
"0134120413 4630412045 0143021675 4013412041 3450341360 5402103251"
"0214306316 502";      /* T. Ace 10/13/2025 */

int main(int argc, const char **argv)
{
    const char *ch;
    int digit, distance, i, j, k, len = 0, max_digit = -1, v[374];
    v[0] = 0;
    printf("vertices:  %x", v[0]);
    for (ch = transitions; *ch; ch++) {
        digit = *ch - '0';
        if (digit >= 0 && digit <= 9) {
            if (++len > 373) {
                printf(" ... snake too long\n");
                return 1;
            }
            v[len] = v[len - 1] ^ (1 << digit);
            if (digit > max_digit) max_digit = digit;
            printf("-%x", v[len]);
        }
    }
    printf("\n");
    for (i = 2; i <= len ; i++) {
        for (j = 0; j <= i - 2; j++) {
            distance = 0;
            for (k = v[i] ^ v[j]; k; k >>= 1) distance += k & 1;
            if (distance <= 1) {
                printf("bad snake:  Hamming distance %d between "
                    "vertices 0x%x and 0x%x\n", distance, v[i], v[j]);
                return 1;
            }
        }
    }
    printf("valid snake.  d=%d  len=%d\n", max_digit + 1, len);
    return 0;
}
```